

β-Diketones in Ring Formation. Part III.

BY UMAPRASANNA BASU.

In earlier parts of this work (Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 482, 815) it has been shown that the methylene group of cyanoacetamide preferentially reacts with the enolic form of a β-diketone to give rise to a pyridone derivative, the yield depending on the nature of the β-substituent in the enolic ketone (I) as it generally governs the course of a Michael's reaction (*cf.* Cooper, Ingold and Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, p. 1869).

The condensation of *p*-toluoylacetone and ethyl benzoylpyruvate with cyanoacetamide has been studied in the present work and the evidence obtained suggests that in each case the yield of the different pyridone derivatives formed depends upon the β-substituent of the respective enolic ketone. When for instance, *p*-toluoylacetone was condensed with cyanoacetamide under the experimental conditions described later, the main product (more than 90% of the total yield) was a crystalline substance (II), the constitution of which was ascertained by its synthesis by other means (*vide infra*). A very small quantity of an isomeric pyridone derivative (III) was isolated from the mother-liquor of the reaction mixture.

(I)

(II)

(III)

p-Toluoylacetone gives with ammonia an amine, $\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{C}(\text{NH}_2) = \text{CH} \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3$, m. p. 93°, which on treatment with cyanoacetamide (see Experimental) gave a well crystalline solid, found to be identical with 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone (II), the main

condensation product derived from the condensation of cyanoacetamide with the β -diketone itself (cf. Sen and Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 437).

Next the *O*-ether (IV) of *p*-toluoylacetone was prepared. This *O*-ether reacted with hydroxylamine (a ketonic reagent) evidently to give rise to 3-*p*-tolyl-5-methyl-isoxazole (VI), m.p. 73-74°, (cf. Claisen, *Ber.*, 1926, 59, 144) as follows: *

Accordingly cyanoacetamide (also a ketonic reagent) might react to form 3-cyano-4-*p*-tolyl-6-methyl-2-pyridone (III). But on condensing the ether (IV) with cyanoacetamide both in presence of Michael's (sodium ethoxide) as well as Knoevenagel's (diethylamine) reagent, only 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone (II) was isolated in almost quantitative yield, the formation of which may be represented in the following way:—

Thus it appears that though the methylene group of cyanoacetamide be regarded as a ketonic reagent, it preferentially reacts with the ethylenic linkage when present in a system as represented in (I) or (IV) (cf. Basu, *loc. cit.*). Further the reaction seems to occur mainly through the enol (VIII) which is lightly substituted in the β -position and the yield of the other pyridone derivative (III) is less than 10 per cent. of the total yield, which is even lower than that obtained in the case of benzoylacetone (cf. Issoglio, *Atti. R. Accad. Sci. Torino*, 1905, 40, 495). This again exhibits a greater inhibiting effect of a

* The other isoxazole derivative 3-methyl-5-*p*-tolyl-isoxazole (VII), m. p. 92°, was obtained by the action of hydroxylamine on *p*-toluoylacetone itself.

still heavier substituent (tolyl) as present in (IX) in comparison with phenyl in (X).

By condensing *p*-toluoylacetone with cyanoacetmethylamide the main product was found to be identical with the *N*-methyl ether, 3-cyano-1:4-dimethyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone (Formula II, NH=N·CH₃) prepared from the pyridone derivative (II).

From the condensation of ethyl benzoylpyruvate with cyanoacetamide a compound, m. p. 229-30°, having the formula C₁₅H₁₂O₃N₂ was obtained. This on hydrolysis with fuming hydrochloric acid gave an acid, m. p. 350°, from which the carboxyl group could not be removed even by direct heating. The compound is regarded as ethyl 3-cyano-6-phenyl-2-pyridine-4-carboxylate (XI) (*cf.* Bardhan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, p. 2223).

Finally another enol ether (XII) has been prepared, and from its condensation with cyanoacetamide 3-cyano-4-anisyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone (XIII), m. p. 314°, alone was obtained. The constitution of the compound was ascertained by condensing the unsaturated ketone, anisalacetophenone (XIV) with sodiocyanoacetamide when 2-keto-3-cyano-4-anisyl-6-phenyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydropyridine (XV), m. p. 204-05°, was obtained. This on dehydrogenation with nitrous acid (Barat, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 330) afforded a product which was found to be identical with (XIII).

EXPERIMENTAL.

p-Toluoylacetone, $\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3(p)$.—Sodium wire (11.5 g.) was suspended in well-cooled dry ethyl acetate (120 g). The whole being kept in a freezing mixture, dry *p*-methylacetophenone (67 g.) was gradually added with shaking, the addition being completed within 2 to 2½ hours, when the sodium salt began to separate. The mixture was left over for 16 to 18 hours in a cool place. The sodium salt was filtered off, washed with ether and dried over porous plate. It was then dissolved in water and decomposed by dilute acetic acid (30%). The separated oil was taken up in ether and the ethereal solution after being washed with water was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The ether was then driven off and the residual liquid was distilled up to 120°. The remaining oil was distilled under reduced pressure and the fraction boiling between 128° and 140° at 15 mm. was collected. On redistillation at the same pressure it was found to boil at 132° (yield 34 g.). (Found: C, 74.92; H, 7.03. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 75.0; H, 6.82 per cent.).

It is a colourless, highly refracting liquid, the refractive index being 1.5378 at 28.5°. It gives a reddish-violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Copper Salt.—On adding a hot solution of copper acetate to an alcoholic solution of the β -diketone, the copper salt separated, and was crystallised from acetone in small greyish-green needles, m.p. 229°. (Found: Cu, 15.76. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{Cu}$ requires Cu, 15.37 per cent.).

Action of Hydroxylamine: Formation of 3-Methyl-5-p-tolyl-isoxazole (VII).—The diketone (2 g.) dissolved in acetic acid was added to an aqueous solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (2 g.) and sodium acetate (4 g.), and the mixture was heated on a water-bath for 3 hours when on cooling crystals separated out. These were filtered off and crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol and obtained in large flakes, m.p. 92°. (Found: N, 8.18. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}$ requires N, 8.09 per cent.).

Action of Hydrazine: Formation of 3-Methyl-5-p-tolylpyrazole.—*p*-Toluoylacetone (3.3 g.) in acetic acid was similarly treated with an aqueous solution hydrazine sulphate (2.5 g.) and sodium acetate (5 g.). On addition of water to the reaction mixture a crystalline solid separated out. This was collected and crystallised from dilute alcohol when prismatic needles, m.p. 125° were obtained. This was, however, found to melt first at 96° when dipped in a hot bath and

then again at 125°. On just melting the substance in a test tube, moisture condensed on the cooler part indicating the presence of water of crystallisation. The pyrazole derivative was dried over sulphuric acid in *vacuo* when it no longer melted below 125° even if dipped in the hot bath, and on melting the substance no moisture condensed in the cooler part of the test tube. (Found: N, 16.34. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2$ requires N, 16.28 per cent.). It is very soluble in alcohol and benzene, and on recrystallisation from *dilute* alcohol melts at 96° when dipped in hot bath as usual.

Action of Aniline: Formation of $CH_3 \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot CO \cdot CH = CMe \cdot NHPH$.—An acetic acid solution of *p*-toluoylacetone (6 g.) and aniline (3.2 g.) was heated under reflux for about 6 hours, and then cooled in ice when a solid separated out. This was collected and crystallised from methyl alcohol (charcoal) when yellow needles, m.p. 136-37° were obtained. (Found: N, 5.69. $C_{17}H_{17}ON$ requires N, 5.58 per cent.).

Action of Ammonia: Formation of $CH_3 \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot CO \cdot CH = CMe \cdot NH_2$.—Dry ammonia was passed into an alcoholic solution (1:1) of the β -diketone for several hours when on dilution with water the amine separated out. This on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and petroleum ether melted at 93°. (Found: N, 8.22. $C_{11}H_{13}ON$ requires N, 8.0 per cent.). It is soluble in most common organic solvents.

An intimate mixture of cyanoacetamide (1 mol.) and the amine (1 mol.) was heated in an oil-bath for more than half an hour at 140° when ammonia was given off and the contents set to a crystalline solid. This on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid formed shining plates, m.p. 330° darkening earlier. (Found: N, 12.58. $C_{14}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 12.50 per cent.). It was found to be identical with the main crop obtained from the condensation of *p*-toluoylacetone and cyanoacetamide described below.

Condensation with Cyanoacetamide: Formation of 3-Cyano-4-methyl-6-p-tolyl-2-pyridone (II) and 3-Cyano-4-p-tolyl-6-methyl-2-pyridone (III).—Cyanoacetamide (4.2 g.) was dissolved in water by warming and *p*-toluoylacetone (8.8 g.) added with just enough alcohol to effect the solution. Diethylamine (2 c.c.) being added, the solution was warmed up to 60° when after 10 minutes crystals began to separate. After about 2 hours the solid (8.1 g.) was collected and was found to melt at 330°, sintering and darkening a few degrees earlier. The mother-liquor with the further addition of diethylamine

(1 c.c.) was left overnight. Next day the crystals (0.8 g.) were filtered off and dried. This also melted at the same temperature. The operation was repeated when a further crop (0.1 g.) having almost the same melting point was obtained. The mother-liquor was then concentrated to half its volume when a solid (1.0 g.), m.p. 259-61°, was obtained. The filtrate on acidification gave another crop (0.7 g.) melting indifferently between 250° and 270°. The total yield of the condensation product was thus about 10.7 g. (95%).

The first three fractions (9.0 g.) were sparingly soluble in alcohol but crystallised out from glacial acetic acid in shining plates with a faint violet reflex, m.p. 330° darkening and sintering earlier. A mixture of this and the product obtained from the amine, $\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{CH} = \text{CMe} \cdot \text{NH}_2$ melted at the same temperature. Accordingly this is considered to be 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone (*cf.* Sen and Basu, *loc. cit.*). (Found: N, 12.2. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{ON}_2$ requires N, 12.5 per cent.). This pyridone derivative is almost insoluble in common organic solvents but readily dissolves in pyridine and boiling glacial acetic acid. It is also soluble in alkali and concentrated sulphuric acid.

Hydrolysis: Formation of 4-Methyl-6-p-tolyl-2-pyridone.—On gently heating the substance with sulphuric acid (80%) for 45 minutes, then pouring the acid solution on ice water and neutralising the solution with solid sodium carbonate, 4-methyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone was obtained. This on crystallisation from alcohol diluted with a few drops of water melted at 183°. (Found: N, 7.0. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{ON}$ requires N, 7.04 per cent.) It is easily soluble in alcohol, benzene, also soluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and insoluble in ether. It dissolves in caustic soda solution and is obtained unchanged on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid. The compound in alcoholic solution also imparts a red coloration to ferric chloride.

3-Cyano-1:4-dimethyl-6-p-tolyl-2-pyridone (II, $\text{N} \cdot \text{CH}_3$ for NH).—To the sodium salt of the pyridone (II) in methyl alcohol, an excess of methyl iodide was added with vigorous shaking. The sodium salt gradually went into solution from which the shining crystals that separated after 12 hours, crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 248°, not depressing when admixed with the *N*-methyl compound described below. (Found: N, 11.95. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{ON}_2$ requires N, 11.77 per cent.).

The other isomer 3-cyano-4-*p*-tolyl-6-methyl-2-pyridone (III) was isolated from the latter fractions of the condensation product. When

the above two fractions (1.7 g.) were boiled with alcohol (90%), an insoluble portion (about 50%), m.p. 270-300°, was left behind which on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid melted at 330-31° and consequently was 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone. While from the mother-liquor a crystalline solid having no sharp melting point was isolated. This however on repeated crystallisation from dilute alcohol melted indifferently at 275° sintering at 260°. (Found: N, 12.50. $C_{14}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 12.50 per cent.). It is also soluble in alkali and sulphuric acid and on hydrolysis with sulphuric acid in the usual way afforded a product which in alcoholic solution gave a brown-red coloration to ferric chloride and on crystallisation from dilute alcohol melted at 253°. Thus it is found that out of the total yield (10.7 g.) of the condensation product the main crop, m.p. 330-31°, constitutes more than 90 per cent.

Condensation of O-Ethyl-p-toluoylacetone (IV) with Cyanoacetamide: Formation of 3-Cyano-4-methyl-6-p-tolyl-2-pyridone (II).—The ethyl ether was prepared according to the method described by Claisen (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 3909) for the preparation of an analogous ether (V) from benzoylacetone. It was a colourless refracting oil, b.p. 163°/15 mm. *p*-Toluoylacetone (17.6 g.), orthoformic ester (15.5 g.) and alcohol (15 g.) were mixed together and to it anhydrous ferric chloride (0.5 g.) was added. The whole was then boiled for 10 minutes under reflux, rapidly cooled in ice and taken in ether. The ethereal solution was washed first with water and then repeatedly with dilute caustic soda solution (2*N*) until the extract gave no appreciable colour to an alcoholic ferric chloride solution. It was then dried over anhydrous calcium chloride, the ether was distilled off and the residual liquid distilled under reduced pressure when a pale yellow oil (11.5 g.) was collected at 185-87° at 28 mm. pressure. This on redistillation at 15 mm. pressure was obtained as an almost colourless oil, b.p. 163°. (Found: C, 76.08; H, 7.68. $C_{13}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 76.47; H, 7.84 per cent.). The refractive index is 1.5510 at 35°. It does not give any coloration to ferric chloride solution (neutral) but on the addition of a drop of hydrochloric acid colour at once develops and gradually changes to reddish-violet, the characteristic test of β -diketone itself.

An alcoholic solution of the oil (4.1 g.) was gradually added with shaking to a suspension of sodiocyanoacetamide prepared from cyanoacetamide (1.7 g.) in hot alcohol and sodium (0.46 g.) also dissolved in absolute alcohol. The colour of the mixture at once became

deeper (yellow) and it was left aside with occasional shaking when a granulated sodium salt began to separate within 3 to 4 hours. After 5 days the separated sodium salt was dissolved in water and the solution was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when a solid (4.4 g.), m.p. 330°, was isolated (yield 98%). From glacial acetic acid it was obtained in beautiful shining crystals with the characteristic violet reflex of 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone and was found to melt at the same temperature when admixed with the above compound already described. The same pyridone derivative was obtained in almost theoretical yield by condensing the ether with cyanoacetamide in alcoholic solution in presence of diethylamine at the temperature of boiling water-bath.

*Action of the Ether on Hydroxylamine: Formation of 3-*p*-Tolyl-5-methylisoxazole (VI).*—An alcoholic solution of *O*-ethyl-*p*-toluoylacetone (2 g.) was added to an aqueous solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (2 g.) and caustic soda (2 g.) and the mixture was heated under reflux on a water-bath for more than an hour. The reaction mixture was then cooled in ice and the solid obtained was collected. Crystallising from methyl alcohol with the addition of a few drops of water it was obtained in minute plates, m. p. 73-74°. (Found: N, 8.17. $C_{11}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 8.09 per cent.).

*Condensation of *p*-Toluoylacetone with Cyanoacetmethylamide: Formation of 3-Cyano-1:4-dimethyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone (II, NH = NCH₃) and 3-Cyano-1:6-dimethyl-4-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone (III, NH = NCH₃).*—The condensation was effected in the usual way in presence of diethylamine (total yield 91%).

The main product (about 92% of the total yield) crystallises from alcohol (90%) in beautiful shining plates with a violet reflex, m. p. 248°, not depressed on admixture with the *N*-methyl ether previously described and evidently it is 3-cyano-1:4-dimethyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone. (Found: N, 12.05. $C_{15}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 11.77 per cent.). This is easily soluble in acetone, chloroform, methyl and ethyl alcohol, moderately so in benzene and carbon tetrachloride, sparingly in boiling water and insoluble in ether. It also dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid, precipitated unchanged on dilution with water and is insoluble in alkali. On hydrolysis with fuming hydrochloric acid at 150-60° for 4 hours the compound afforded a solid product which on crystallisation from dilute hydrochloric acid was obtained in fine prismatic needles, m.p. 188°. (Found: N, 5.50; Cl, 13.98. $C_{14}H_{15}ON, HCl$ requires N, 5.61; Cl, 14.23 per cent.).

It is a hydrochloride, and when heated to its melting point vapours of hydrogen chloride evolve. The compound gives no coloration to alcoholic ferric chloride.

The product from mother-liquor (0.4 g.), m.p. 158-78°, on twice crystallisation from dilute alcohol melted indifferently at 175-76° sintering earlier. This is regarded as the other isomer 3-cyano-1:6-dimethyl-4-p-tolyl-2-pyridone. (Found: N, 11.76. $C_{15}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 11.77 per cent.).

Condensation of Ethyl Benzoylpyruvate with Cyanoacetamide: Formation of Ethyl 3-Cyano-6-phenyl-2-pyridone-4-carboxylate (XI).—The condensation was effected as usual by means of diethylamine at the room temperature, the yield being more than 70%. The condensation product crystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellow needles having a green reflex, m. p. 229-30. (Found: N, 10.54. $C_{15}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10.45 per cent.). It is insoluble in water but soluble in alcohol and acetic acid. It dissolves in alkali with a beautiful violet fluorescence and also in concentrated sulphuric acid. On hydrolysis with fuming hydrochloric acid at 170-75° for more than 4 hours the above pyridone derivative afforded an acid which on crystallisation from a large volume of glacial acetic acid melted at 350°. (Found: N, 6.63. $C_{12}H_9O_3N$ requires N, 6.51 per cent.). It is insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in pyridine, sodium bicarbonate solution with effervescence and in concentrated sulphuric acid. The acid may also be obtained by simply heating the pyridone derivative with caustic soda solution (10%) for a short time.

Ethyl 1-Methyl-3-cyano-6-phenyl-2-pyridone-4-carboxylate (XI, NH=N·CH₃).—The pyridone derivative dissolved in sodium methoxide solution containing the required quantity of sodium was treated with methyl iodide till the solution was found neutral. Excess of methyl alcohol was distilled off and the oil that was left behind, soon solidified. Water was added and the remaining solid was collected and dried over porous plate. On crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and petroleum ether it was obtained in rhombic yellow plates, m. p. 150°. (Found: N, 10.26. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.93 per cent.). It is very soluble in almost all organic solvents except petroleum ether in which it is insoluble. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a green fluorescence but is insoluble in cold alkali. On boiling however its solution in warm alkali and on acidifying the solution, an acid, m. p. 253°, was obtained.

Condensation of O-Methylanisoylacetophenone, $\text{CH}_3\text{O}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{C}(\text{OCH}_3)=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{Ph}$ (XII) with Cyanoacetamide: Formation of 3-Cyano-4-anisyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone (XIII).—The methyl ether was prepared according to Weygand (*Annalen*, 1927, 459, 113) and its condensation with cyanoacetamide effected in the usual way (yield 50%). The product on crystallisation from pyridine was obtained in fine needles, m. p. 314° . (Found: N, 9.02. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 9.27 per cent.). It is almost insoluble in alcohol, sparingly so in glacial acetic acid but dissolves in alkali and concentrated sulphuric acid. That the compound is 3-cyano-4-anisyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone is proved from the following investigations.

Condensation of Anisalacetophenone (XIV) with Cyanoacetamide: Formation of 2-Keto-3-cyano-4-anisyl-6-phenyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydropyridine (XV).—Anisalacetophenone, was prepared according to Pond and Shoffstali (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 22, 666) and Weygand (*loc. cit.*). An alcoholic solution of the unsaturated ketone (1 mol.) was treated with sodiocyanoacetamide (1 mol.) as usual. After 4 days water was added to the reaction mixture and the condensation product was obtained by acidulation with dilute hydrochloric acid. Crystallising from alcohol (90%) it was obtained in clusters of needles, m.p. $204\text{--}05^\circ$. (Found: C, 75.58; H, 5.57; N, 9.24. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires C, 75.01; H, 5.26; N, 9.21 per cent.). This compound is also soluble in concentrated sulphuric acid.

Dehydrogenation: Formation of 3-Cyano-4-anisyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone (XIII).—The above pyridine derivative (2 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and cooled in ice when a similarly well cooled solution of sodium nitrite (1 g.) was slowly added to it. The flask was left for two hours in the ice-bath and then overnight at the room temperature. Next day the solid that separated out was collected and on crystallisation from pyridine (charcoal) was obtained in fine needles, m. p. 314° sintering two or three degrees earlier (Found: N, 8.95. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 9.27 per cent.). This was found to melt at the same temperature when admixed with the compound obtained from the condensation of *O*-methylanisoylacetophenone (XIII) with cyanoacetamide just described.

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